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State Channel as a Service Based on a Distributed and Decentralized Web

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ABSTRACT Currently, developers and researchers are dedicated to finding better ways to achieve greater scalability of various blockchain platforms. Focused on the Ethereum blockchain platform, the state channels are currently the only maturely researched and implemented a solution for achieving scalability. However, there are still several problems, such as transparency of state channel networks, transaction traceability, and the incapability that the off-chain state is transferred back on the blockchain network in an ad-hoc manner. To solve the aforementioned problems, we propose a novel state channel solution in the form of a State Channel as a Service, which, although off-chain, still incorporates a secure distributed and decentralized network. This solves the challenge of transparency and traceability while giving users the confidence that only the valid last off-chain state is transferred back on the blockchain network. With the proposed solution, there is no need for users to monitor state channel activities for possible malicious actions. Implementation was performed in the form of a payment channel system, presenting a potential use case for the SCaaS. Furthermore, we performed a security and performance analysis, which shows that the solution is secure and by a factor of 12 more efficient than the classical on-chain payment systems. To evaluate and prove the contributions of the proposed solution, quantitative, and qualitative comparisons with selected related works (i.e., Raiden and Celer) were also performed.

INDEX TERMS Blockchain, distributed, decentralized, scalability, ethereum, state channels, off-chain.

I. INTRODUCTION

Blockchain technology has recently attracted much interest in the general public, as well by various companies that are interested in the possibility of exploiting this technology in order to support their existing business processes or to develop potential new business models. When using the most stable and popular public blockchain platforms, certain weaknesses of these are to be recognized and acknowledged. One of the main weaknesses is certainly scalability. As an example, the Ethereum platform can process only 7 - 15 transactions per second, which in most cases is significant to low for enterprise adoption [1]. Multiple attempts at solving the scalability problem already exist, e.g., introducing state channels, side-chaining [2], [3], and Plasma [4]. In this paper, we limit ourselves to the Ethereum platform, as a platform with the most active developers and researchers, compared to other blockchain platforms [5], and on the topic of solving the

scalability problem with the introduction of state channels, through which users can transfer an (on-chain) state outside the blockchain network (i.e., off-chain), where it can be manipulated multiple times without the built-in restrictions of the blockchain network, including the fees, etc. Furthermore, the state channel enables that, at some point, the off-chain state is transferred back to the blockchain network and merged with the last valid on-chain state [6]–[8].

Existing solutions that involve the use of the state channels face the challenge of preventing abuses, caused by users involved in the state channel in the process of transferring the off-chain state back to the blockchain network. Since users alone define the new state, which is to be transferred back to the blockchain network, there is a possibility that the defined state is not necessarily last valid and agreed upon by all involved parties in the off-chain environment (i.e., off-chain state channel). The most common way to solve such a problem is to introduce a disputed time. When an off-chain state is transferred back on-chain, there is a defined amount of time within other state channel users who have time to detect

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and prevent a possible malicious attempt. If such an attempt is detected, involved state channel users can propose another (not necessarily last valid, but necessarily newer than previous proposed) version of the off-chain state to be transferred to the blockchain network. If the last proposed off-chain state is indeed more recent than the previous one, it is determined inside on-chain defined mechanisms (i.e., smart contract) [6], [9]. Still, these mechanisms can not guarantee that the real last valid off-chain state is transferred back to the blockchain network, neither that the off-chain state is transferred in an ad-hoc manner.

In most cases, proposed solutions introduce penalty systems for malicious users who intentionally propose not valid states. Furthermore, the proposed solutions enable the prevention of such abuses only by delegating this task to the state channels users themselves. If users want to detect such malicious intentions and actions by themselves, they are required to monitor other involved party's activities constantly. If the channel users are not monitoring the state channel activities or they are absent throughout the dispute time, the malicious user can successfully transfer a non-valid off-chain state to the blockchain network, where this state is permanently accepted as the new valid on-chain state, and such an action cannot be reversed.

In this work, we propose a novel state channel system, which tackles the above-mentioned problems, while still enabling the main features of those (i.e., reducing transaction costs and improving transaction speed). We propose a State Channel as a Service solution (SCaaS), based on a trusted, decentralized, and distributed file storage system. Due to its architectural model, the solution prevents the transfer of non-valid off-chain states to the blockchain network. This is achieved by introducing a trusted off-chain mechanism, which stores the last valid off-chain state in a secure, immutable, trustworthy, and transparent way. The mechanism is based on a distributed, decentralized, but still trusted file storage system IPFS, which incorporates blockchain-like features (e.g., immutability, and transparency) [10]. Furthermore, the solution allows any involved state channel user an ad hoc transfer of the off-chain state back on-chain, without having to wait for a dispute time, while other involved parties do not have to worry about the integrity of the state.

Besides presenting an architectural model for the proposed solution, we also present a detailed overview of a SCaaS prototype. Furthermore, we performed a security and performance analysis in order to prove the feasibility, security, and efficiency of the proposed solution. We also conducted a qualitative and quantitative comparison of our prototype solution with the two other most mature solutions on the state channel area (i.e., Raiden and Celer Network).

The contributions of this work can be summarized as:

- A new state channel architecture, which incorporates the notion of a trusted distributed and decentralized network.
- Operations performed outside the blockchain network are fully transparent and immutable.

- The solution is a general one, which can be applied to other sub-types of state channels (e.g., payment channels).
- The solution enables users to instantly transfer off-chain states back to the blockchain network (ad-hoc), without having to wait for dispute times.
- A mechanism that prevents abuse from malicious users in the process of transferring the off-chain state to the blockchain network.

II. RELATED WORKS

Several solutions were proposed in the field of scaling the Ethereum blockchain network using state channel. Coleman *et al.* [9] propose a state channel framework called Counterfactual that helps blockchain developers to understand the state channels principles and provide the guidelines for building state channels infrastructure. Authors present the fundamental principles and architecture of state channels, whereby some of these principles were taken into consideration while designing our proposed system (e.g., state deposits, multisignature wallets, digital signatures).

Poon and Dryja [6] introduce an implementation including bi-directional payment channels, where payments can be performed in the separated off-chain payment channel network instead of on-chain (i.e., Bitcoin blockchain network) [6]. They propose a solution for possible resolution of disputes that can occur when transferring the off-chain state into the blockchain network. It envisages a certain amount of time in which the users can prove that the state, with which the channel is intended to be closed, is wrong.

Raiden Network is a payment channel network that features the use of the same concepts as that proposed by Poon *et al.*, but within the Ethereum blockchain network. Payment channels are established by Ethereum smart contracts. However, for using Raiden, there is a requirement that every participant is also part of the Raiden network with a running Raiden node. Within the Raiden network, participants, if there is a valid route, can also perform off-chain payments among each other without the directly established channel. When users are transferring the off-chain state into the blockchain network, an irregularity may occur, and the solution, therefore, provides a dispute time after which the transfer of the state is completed if no irregularity has been proven at that time by a channel users [8].

Dong *et al.* [11] introduce a state channel solution that operates on top of a network of the state channel with the incorporation of a side blockchain network. The solution addresses problems mentioned above (e.g., the closure of state channels by not necessarily last valid state), with a crypto-economic layer named cEconomy. If there is a need that the state channel network user goes offline, he stores off-chain state to the special side blockchain network. This side blockchain network consists of agents, who stakes Celer tokens, and their role is to monitor state channel disputes for the user. The main goal with this approach is to build the insurance model where state channel users are secured from

transferring not valid off-chain state to the blockchain network while agents upon payment, monitor state channel for them. If some of the agents do not perform his job, or somehow acts maliciously, this lead to loose of his staked tokens.

McCorry *et al.* [12] propose a solution including a third party which, in the absence of a channel user, monitors the eventual closure of the channel. If such a party detects the channel closure with an invalid state, initiates a dispute on its behalf. The specific design of the state channel network also offers a solution in case of dispute resolution involving such third parties, which can occur when the off-chain state is transferred to the blockchain network.

Several other works are performed in the state channel field but are primarily focused on building effective state channel networks [11]–[16], while the construction of the individual state channel follows the characteristics presented in the proposed Counterfactual framework [9].

To the best of our knowledge no solution exists, which proposes an off-chain architecture (e.g., state channel), whereby operations performed off-chain are faster and cheaper than those on-chain, while still incorporating features as those of the blockchain network, i.e., immutability, transparency, traceability, and integrity. At the moment, there is also no state channel solution which can be used as a service, without a need for users to join another peer to peer network (e.g., Raiden, Celer Network, Lightning network) and run their software to use state channel features.

III. PRELIMINARIES

In this section, we present a short overview of the concepts and technologies that are used in the design of our proposed system.

A. STATE CHANNEL

A state in the Ethereum blockchain network is the last state of a defined and stored variable in a smart contract, which can be accessed and manipulated by users who have the privileges to change it. Every time a state of a variable has to be changed, a transaction call has to be performed on the smart contract, which in turn requires gas and thus implies costs for a user.

The state channel method enables a state from the blockchain network to be transferred outside of it, where predefined users have the right to change it without any costs. After they change it as much as they deem necessary, the new (changed) state is then transferred back to the blockchain network.

The change of the state in such an (off-chain) way is executed and valid immediately, while users do not have to pay any transaction fees for each transaction but only for the last state update [6], [7], [9], [12], [13], [15], [17].

B. MULTI SIGNATURE SMART CONTRACT

A multi-signature principle basically defines a logic, where some action can only be performed if approved and signed by those who are part of the predefined multi-signature

agreement. The agreement itself can require all parties to agree or some predefined number of those.

In such a sense, a multi-signature smart contract (MSSC) is defined and deployed in the blockchain network and defines a state, which is the main artifact of the multi-signature agreement between predefined users of a state channel. With such a smart contract, the transfer of a state outside the blockchain network is enabled, and after the off-chain change is completed, the new state is transferred back in the blockchain network, only if all parties agree and sign such a newly generated state within this multi-signature smart contract [9], [18], [19].

C. ORACLE

An oracle, in the notion of the blockchain technology, defines a trustable agent whose task it is to transfer data from resources outside of the blockchain network to a smart contract deployed in it since the smart contracts cannot retrieve data outside the blockchain network by themselves [20], [21].

D. INTERPLANETARY FILE SYSTEM

InterPlanetary file system (IPFS) is a peer-to-peer distributed and decentralized file system [10]. It is defined by a combination of systems and protocols: (1) distributed hash tables for the maintenance and coordination of system metadata, (2) file exchange across the system via the BitTorrent protocol, (3) file distribution using version control system Git, and (4) transparent system encryption, as well as authentication using self-Certified file systems. The hash value of this object identifies each object stored in the network. This value is then used as a path with which the content of an object stored in such a network is accessed, meaning objects in the IPFS are accessed via its hash and not via its location as this is common in the HTTP protocol. This is possible because each object stored in the IPFS system is replicated throughout the network and can thus be accessed from any of the network nodes since each node also maintains a hash table for each object.

Since all files stored in the IPFS system are permanent, it means that any changes to the already existing files in the system result in a separate new file that needs to be saved in the IPFS system. To overcome this feature, an InterPlanetary Name System (IPNS) system is used, which operates within the same distributed and decentralized network as the IPFS system [10]. A system such as IPNS can generate a fixed address that points to a file stored in the IPFS network. The query about the content of such a fixed address indirectly points to the content of that file. The content of IPNS, which represents the address of a file stored in the IPFS network, can be updated to any other IPFS file address. After updating, the same IPNS address points to another file within the IPFS network [10].

IV. PROPOSED SOLUTION

This section introduces the architecture of the proposed solution, its key components, and what is their role within the overall architecture.

FIGURE 1. High-level architecture of the proposed solution, and interactions between the SCaaS components during the *Initiate state channel function*.

A. SOLUTION OVERVIEW

The proposed solution in the form of a State Channel as a Service (SCaaS), enables the creation of a state channel by which the state defined in the blockchain network is transferred off-chain. User accounts that are defined within a successfully established channel can change the state without the need to communicate with the blockchain network. With such a channel, users can perform transactions without any fees to be paid, and the state is changed immediately, without waiting for the transaction to be mined. These advantages are achieved by incorporating an oracle in the core of the SCaaS, which serves as the objective state protector while storing all state changes in a distributed and decentralized IPFS network. Such an approach enables the transparency of executed transactions on the same level as blockchain technology. The proposed solution allows any user-defined within the channel to complete the changing of an off-chain state, resulting in the transfer of the last valid off-chain state back to the blockchain network. In the proposed solution, users do not have to worry about the time when the channel is closed and if it is closed with a last valid off-chain state that is accepted by all state channel users. Furthermore, they also do not have to watch for the case a malicious user wants to close the channel.

B. SOLUTION COMPONENTS

The proposed solution of the SCaaS, which high-level architecture is shown in Figure 1, consists of the following three key components, which are described in detail below:

- Channel Client-side Application (CCLISA),
- Channel Server-side Application (CSERSA), and
- Multi-Signature Smart Contract (MSSC).

As such, the SCaaS can be viewed as an interaction between the on- and off-chain environment. The former consists of the Ethereum blockchain network, including the MSSC key component. The Ethereum network can be a private, public, main, or test network. The latter environment consists of both the CCLISA and CSERSA key component, as well as an IPFS network, which again can be a private or a public one.

CCLISA is a web application in which logic is supported by the MSSC deployed in the blockchain network and by the CSERSA component, both described below. It enables users to transfer the last valid on-chain state outside the blockchain (off-chain), and afterward in a renewed version back on-chain. The application also allows users to manipulate the off-chain state in a user-friendly manner.

CSERSA is the central component of the proposed SCaaS, whose main task is to ensure the consistency of state

manipulation outside the blockchain network. It also represents the main link between the on- and off-chain environment, as it is the only component in the proposed system that can determine the valid last state outside the blockchain network when requested. The essential task of the component is the integration of external networks such as the IPFS and blockchain networks. The IPFS serves as the medium for securely exchanging the new state proposals, whereby enabling integrity and traceability. CSERSA furthermore forms a complete state channel service together with the CCLISA component. Due to such integration, this component ensures two different functions: (1) in a transparent and distributed way, ensuring the possibility of changing the off-chain state; (2) upon the transfer of the off-chain state back in the blockchain network, ensuring that the transferred state is consistent and valid. Due to the task presented in the second role, the CSERSA can also be viewed as an oracle, since communication with the blockchain network and the MSSC is required. In order to execute the tasks presented in the second role, the CSERSA has to have its own digital identity.

MSSC is the component of the proposed system, through which users agree on a predefined state to be transferred outside the blockchain network. The implementation follows the principles of a classical multi-signature smart contract with some additional specific functions, such as *open*, *check current stage*, *join*, *cancel* and *close state channel*. The individual function can be executed according to the currently assigned stage of the component. Following three stages are possible:

- INIT - the user successfully opened the channel, and MSSC component is deployed into the blockchain network;
- OPEN - all users that were defined when opening the channel joined the state channel;
- CLOSED - one of the users closed the channel;
- CANCELED – the channel is aborted by the user who initiated the state channel.

C. DETAILED SOLUTION ARCHITECTURE

The CCLISA component is comprised of the following five main functions from the user's perspective.

1) INITIATE STATE CHANNEL

The process of initiating a new state channel is depicted in Figure 1 and begins with a user request to open the state channel (Figure 1 - step 1). The user must define the following input parameters: *opposite channel users* and *the state*. *The opposite channel user* is the user with whom the first user wants to open the channel. The defined *state* is the de facto state that will be manipulated outside the blockchain network. Based on the user's input parameters, a JSON file is generated, which will hold the state outside the blockchain network and is afterward used in all future functions, related to the proposed system (Figure 1 - step 2, 3). After being generated, the JSON file is then returned to the initial user

(Figure 1 - step 4). Using the CCLISA component, the initial user digitally signs the JSON file (Figure 1 - step 5). The JSON file with the initial user's digital signature is then added as an input parameter of the CSERSA component function *Pre-open state channel* (Figure 1 – step 6), where it will be additionally digitally signed by the CSERSA component. Thus, the digital signature of the user, as well as the CSERSA digital signature, are added to the JSON file.

At the next step (Figure 1 - step 7, 8), the JSON file, as the carrier of the last state, is being stored on the IPFS network, which represents the medium over which the state changes are carried on. By incorporating such a network, the proposed solutions include blockchain-like features in an off-chain manner, i.e., integrity, traceability, and immutability. A new IPNS ID is generated in the IPFS network, which will serve as an entry point, that will later point to the last valid JSON file holding the last valid off-chain state of a particular state channel. The IPNS ID is then stored in a CSERSA local key-value database as the key with the default value "false", indicating that currently, no process is associated with this key, i.e., JSON file. Thus, the local database is used in all functions in order to prevent simultaneous status changes at the same time, which would, in turn, mean the possibility of generating a non-valid off-chain state. The newly created JSON file is then added to the IPFS network (Figure 1 – step 9, 10). The result of storing a file on the IPFS network is the so-called IPFS hash value of the file, which enables access to the file on the network. As a result of the *Pre-open state channel* function, the IPNS ID value is returned to CCLISA component (Figure 1 – step 11). Returned IPNS ID value belongs to the newly initiated channel and IPFS hash, which represents a link to the JSON file stored in the distributed IPFS network. It should be noted that at this point, no interaction with the blockchain environment was yet performed.

In the next step, the channel, proposed and initiated by one user, has to be accepted by the proposed opposite user, in a way that an agreement is signed and an MSSC formed, which in turn will handle the state transfer from and to the blockchain network. After performing the first two functions, the MSSC is created and deployed to the blockchain network by the user who requested to open the state channel, with the following input parameters: *IPNS ID*, *opposite channel users* and *the state* (Figure 1 – step 14). The address of the newly created MSSC in the blockchain network is returned (Figure 1 – step 15), which, together with the previously obtained IPFS hash, is included as the input parameter in the CSERSA component function call *Check and initiate state channel* (Figure 1 - step 16). The function establishes a connection with MSSC from the blockchain network and performs a query about the on-chain data (Figure 1 - step 17, 18). According to the data returned from the MSSC, CSERSA generates a JSON file, adding the initial state value and digitally signs it. Using the IPFS hash input parameter, a query is made to the distributed file storage IPFS, whereas a result of the JSON file, which was added to the IPFS network in steps 9 and 10, is returned (Figure 1 - step 19, 20).

CSERSA extracts the appropriate values (i.e., opposite channel users, the state) from the returned JSON file and compares it with data from the newly signed JSON file. The comparison must return the result of equality, meaning that both JSON files operate with the same data. This step is necessary because a potentially malicious user could try to modify the actual state, which is held off-chain. In the next step, the local database checks that the IPNS ID acquired from the MSSC related to the opening state channel is not associated with any operation throughout the system. When the condition in a local database is satisfied, a value related to IPNS ID is changed from the value false - indicating that there are currently no operations associated with this IPNS ID to value true. After that, the value which is stored in the IPFS network can be accessed through the IPNS ID, which is provided as an input parameter (Figure 1 – step 21, 22). When the IPFS ID value is successfully assigned to the IPFS hash, the IPNS ID value in the local database is set to false. From that moment, the IPNS ID allows access to the last valid off-chain state stored in an IPFS network. In the end, the CCLISA component informs the user (Figure 1 - step 23, 24), that a state channel has successfully been initiated.

2) CANCEL STATE CHANNEL

During the initiate state channel stage, the user who runs it has to define the opposite channel user. If the indicated opposite user does not join the initiated state channel, the initial user can execute this function to close it. Consequently, the state in the blockchain network will never be transferred off-chain, thus it remains the same as before the state channel was initiated.

3) JOIN STATE CHANNEL

Through this function, all defined opposite users can become part of the initiated state channel and thus open it, hence gather the right to manipulate the on-chain state in an off-chain manner. It should be noted that state channel users interact with the MSSC over the CCLISA, which holds all the required information (e.g., MSSC address), with which a user-friendly interaction is enabled.

4) CHANGE CHANNEL STATE

The process of changing an off-chain state is depicted in Figure 2 and begins with a user request (Figure 2 - arrow A). The user must define the proposed *new state*, while the CCLISA component includes the appropriate MSSC address. With these parameters, the *Pre-change channel state* function defined by CSERSA component is called (Figure 2 - arrow B). The IPNS ID stored for the state channel in which we change the off-chain state is also obtained from the MSSC component. Based on the acquired IPNS ID value, the IPFS hash value is obtained, by which it is possible to access the last valid JSON file, which is stored within the distributed storage, and in this case, represents the last valid off-chain state.

FIGURE 2. Interactions between the SCaaS components during the Change channel state and during the Close state channel function.

Next, it is verified that the address from which the new off-chain state proposal comes from, is part of the state channel. Based on the currently valid off-chain state obtained from the JSON file, the system verifies that the newly proposed state is valid. It should be noted that the rules, within which the validation of the newly proposed state is performed, can be adjusted depending on the purpose of the proposed state channel system. After the successful validation, a JSON file with the proposed new state is generated. Furthermore, in the newly generated JSON file under the property “Link previous IPFS file”, the IPFS hash value of the current last valid JSON file, and thus the off-chain state is added. JSON file also contains a property “Nonce” which represents the sequence number of the off-chain state, and it is incremented within off-chain state update. An example depiction of this can be seen in Figure 3. This ensures a reference to the previous valid off-chain state and guarantees the traceability feature of the proposed SCaaS solution. As a result, the JSON file is passed on to the CCLISA component (Figure 2 - arrow B).

The content of the newly generated JSON file is then presented to the user by the CCLISA component and proposed

FIGURE 3. JSON file structure and traceability assurance within the IPFS network.

for his acceptance and thus signature (Figure 2 - arrow A). The JSON file with the user’s digital signature (Figure 2 - arrow A) is then added as the input parameter of the *Check and change channel state* function defined by CSERSA component (Figure 2 - arrow B). Next, IPNS ID is obtained from the MSSC component deployed in the blockchain network. Based on the value of the IPNS ID, the JSON file stored on IPFS distributed storage is retrieved in the same manner as described before. Based on the user’s proposed new off-chain state, the system generates its JSON file, representing the state-channel service proposal of the new off-chain state. After that, data from both JSON files are compared. In the case of matching, the system considers the user’s proposal to be accepted as valid. User’s and CSERSA’s digital signature, as well as the content of the JSON file, which represents the proposed new off-chain state, are then added to a newly created JSON file, which is stored in the IPFS network. After that, the IPNS ID value of the state channel is updated to hold the new IPFS hash of the aforementioned JSON file in order to point to the currently last valid off-chain state. The process of changing the IPNS ID value is performed in the same manner as in the before described *Check and open state channel* function. The information that the off-chain state is updated is then forwarded to CCLISA component (Figure 2 – arrow B). The result of the proposed off-chain state change is then reported to the user (Figure 2 - arrow A), which means that the system successfully checked and updated the off-chain state inside the state channel service to the latest valid version that was proposed by one of the system users.

5) CLOSE STATE CHANNEL

The process of closing the state channel is shown in Figure 2 and starts with the call of the function *close state*

channel (Figure 2 - arrow A). The function can be called by any defined state channel user, who wants to end up with an off-chain manner state changing. With this, the process of transferring the last valid off-chain state back to the blockchain network is started. A digital signature request is provided to the user with a text message confirming the closure of the state channel (Figure 2 - arrow A). The digital signature, the message, and the address of the MSSC component deployed in a blockchain network are given as the input parameters of the *Close state channel function* of the CSERSA component (Figure 2 – arrow A, B). Based on the IPNS ID value obtained from the MSSC component deployed on the blockchain network, the proper JSON file is acquired from the IPFS network. Prior to this, a verification of the user who calls the close state channel is performed, which checks if the user is part of the state channel. Based on the acquired IPNS ID and its value from the local key-value database, it is verified that the current off-chain state within the state channel is not the subject of any other manipulation, e.g., changing channel state or closing the channel by other users. The state extracted from the JSON file is added to a transaction, signed by the CSERSA component, and transferred to the MSSC component on the blockchain network. To ensure blockchain features (e.g., immutability, and transparency) of the proposed solution, the JSON file remains permanently stored in the IPFS network. From this moment, the off-chain state from the SCaaS system became a valid state on the blockchain network. Finally, the channel is now permanently closed. After successful closure of the channel, the CSERSA component informs the CCLISA component, which sent a message to the user (Figure 2 – arrow B, A).

V. SECURITY EVALUATION

A security analysis of the proposed solution was performed. It should be noted that the analysis did not cover the Ethereum blockchain protocol and possible attacks on private keys, as well as not the IPFS protocol, because we assume that these protocols are safe. The most critical scenarios for end-users that can occur during system operation are described below.

A. MAN-IN-THE-MIDDLE ATTACK

For security reasons, every action performed through the system requires a user to sign his action digitally. Data, in the majority cases, the JSON files, which have to be signed by the user, are retrieved from the server-side component of our system (CSERSA). The user performs the signing process itself over the client-side component (CCLISA). This opens the door for a malicious data modification prior to the signing process of the user, since a malicious eavesdropping user could mount a man-in-the-middle attack. In order to prevent such a scenario, a validity check of the provided data is required.

There are two possible malicious entry points in our system, where a malicious user can modify data generated for the digital signing process, i.e., in the *initiate* and *change channel state functions*. In the initiate state channel function,

the generated data, which also includes user and oracle digital signature, is passed in the constructor parameters of the MSSC component and as a transaction deployed on the blockchain network. Meanwhile, the signed JSON file is also stored on the IPFS network. Because the transaction is signed through the CCLISA component, the data could potentially be modified, which would result in the deployment of an MSSC based on non-valid and malicious data.

If the user wants to initiate a state channel successfully, the MSSC address and the IPFS hash of data must be sent to the CSERSA component. Based on the retrieved data, the oracle generates a new JSON file and digitally signs it. Because the part of data retrieved from the IPFS network is also oracle digital signature, the system can check if these signatures are matching. This guarantees that the JSON file has not been changed from start to the end of the initiate state channel process. If the signatures are matching, the IPNS ID is updated, and the off-chain state is confirmed as valid.

In the case of the *change state channel function*, users propose the new state chain through the CCLISA component. Based on their input parameters, the new proposed off-chain state is added to a newly generated JSON file through the CSERSA component. It is then returned to CCLISA component, where the system requires the users to digitally sign the file. The JSON file, including the digital signatures, is then sent back to CSERSA component, where the off-chain state is finally changed. A possible attack can be mounted if the attacker modifies the generated JSON file, digitally signs it, and sends such a modified file back to the CCLISA component, which could lead to the fact that the malicious proposed off-chain state is being accepted as valid. In order to prevent such an attack, the newly proposed off-chain state validity is always double-checked before the IPNS ID is changed and with the new state confirmed as a new last off-chain state.

B. SIMULTANEOUS CHANGING OF STATES

A possibility exists that multiple operations are performed simultaneously on the same state, e.g., changing the off-chain state by one user, while trying to close the state channel by another. Because the operations are performed over the same data, such behavior may lead to wrong results. In order to prevent such scenarios, the proposed system incorporates a locking mechanism with which simultaneous and conflicting operations are prevented.

The locking mechanism is based on the local key-value database and a flag system. If one user is changing a state in an off-chain manner, the state itself gets a dedicated flag in the key-value database, which disables any other change to the same state, while the last one is not processed and accepted. This means that any number of simultaneous operations on an off-chain state can be attempted without the possibility that the wrong results can be produced.

C. ORACLE UNCERTAINTY

One of the main requirements for the end-user is the certainty that the SCaaS based oracle will truly transfer the last valid

off-chain state back to the blockchain network when this is required. CSERSA component is server-side oriented. There is a probability that this component, for some reason, became unavailable for the close channel requests. If this occurs, there is a risk that users can not transfer off-chain state back to the blockchain network. To prevent such a scenario, the SCaaS is designed to enable users to close the state channel manually even though the CSERSA component is unavailable. This is enabled through the interaction with the MSSC component deployed on the blockchain network, which enables users to close the state channel by the conventional approach [9] i.e., with some minor differences. After the transaction on the MSSC component is sent, a unique Ethereum event from the MSSC component is emitted, which is stored in the blockchain ledger. When the CSERSA component is operational again, it starts querying the ledger for possible emitted transaction events. In the case that the state channel is not already closed due to the conventional mechanism, the CSERSA component closes the state channel automatically as described in Section IV-C.5, thus aborts the conventional approach. Because of above presented feature, the users can be confident that despite the SCaaS unavailability, the off-chain state can be successfully and securely transferred on the blockchain network.

Despite the potential SCaaS unavailability, the off-chain state within the proposed solution is transferred back to the blockchain network faster than in other related state channel solutions. This is backed up by the fact given by Wu *et al.* [22], which assumes that high availability business applications downtime (e.g., SCaaS) is less than 5 min/per annum. The minimum dispute time in the related state channel solutions is more than that (e.g., Raiden network - on the Ropsten test network 500 blocks \approx 108,3 min/per channel close).

D. ORACLE CREDIBILITY

In comparison with other state channel solutions, our proposed solution enables the transfer of an off-chain state to the blockchain network in an ad-hoc manner. Within this process, there are no additional requirements as waiting for dispute times and monitoring for potential malicious close channel attempts. However, some doubts about oracle fairness exist, which are evaluated below. The close state channel function inside the MSSC component involves security mechanisms to prevent the oracle from trying to close the channel with an off-chain state, which is not necessarily valid. The mechanism inside the MSSC component validates both (oracle and user) provided digital signatures of off-chain state. Validation is successful only if the special flag in the form of text: "Close state channel with this data." is appended to the off-chain state, which is digitally signed. With this mechanism, the possibility that oracle closes the channel with the not valid off-chain state for a particular state channel is annulled. To additionally ensure that the oracle functions (e.g., close state channel) are correctly executed, the CSERSA component can be deployed inside a trusted execution

environment (TEE). With this, a secure environment that guarantees the integrity and confidentiality of code and data inside is established [23].

E. DATA INTEGRITY

The integrity of the data (e.g., off-chain state) with which the proposed solution performs operations is achievable through the implementation of JSON files holding the last valid state. The JSON file is considered secure due to the involvement of users and systems digital signatures and the fact that these files are stored on a distributed and decentralized file storage system (IPFS). Furthermore, the proposed solution enables full traceability of state changes through the IPNS protocol and again through JSON files, which are linked together via a JSON parameter pointing to the previous JSON file's IPFS location. This ensures that the system always has access to the last valid JSON file and the off-chain state since the IPNS ID holding the last valid JSON file is stored in the MSSC component deployed on the blockchain network.

Figure 3 presents an example of three linked JSON files holding all the required data, whereby the information itself is part of a payment channel system implementation, i.e., *address_a*, *balance_a*, *address_b*, and *balance_b* attributes. The number of off-chain state updates is stored inside attribute *nonce*. Attribute *prev_state* stores the IPFS hash as a link to the previous JSON file holding the previous valid off-chain state of this channel. The digital signature of the user who performs the change is stored in the *user_sig* attribute. Oracle's signature is stored in the *oracle_sig* attribute and confirms that SCaaS verified this state.

F. SCaaS BYPASSING ATTACK

Because the MSSC Component is deployed on the blockchain network, there is a possibility that users bypass SCaaS and tries to communicate directly with the MSSC. Directly communication cannot be prevented, because the MSSC is deployed in an Ethereum blockchain network, where anyone can participate in the interaction with it.

If the user performs a transaction which opens state channel directly to the MSSC, with the required data (i.e., IPNS ID, opposite users, state), thus bypassing the SCaaS, the transaction will be successfully executed, but the IPNS ID at that moment is not pointing to any JSON file stored on the IPFS network. The IPNS ID value can be updated to an appropriate JSON file only by using the SCaaS. If IPNS ID is not updated, the state is not successfully transferred off-chain and cannot be changed in an off-chain manner despite the fact, that the MSSC component contains the data about opened state channel.

A user could also perform a join operation on the MSSC, without incorporating the SCaaS, but there are no security concerns in such an act, since if this user is defined as one of the state channel users when the state channel was initiated, then this is a legitimate action. On the contrary, if the user interacting with the MSSC directly, is not defined as a part

of the state channel, then his attempt to join the channel is reverted by the MSSC component.

To ensure that the off-chain state in case of the SCaaS unavailability (i.e., CSERSA component) can be transferred back to the blockchain network, we included additional features described in Section V-C. Within this, the close state channel operation can be performed directly on the MSSC component. In case the CSERSA component is available, and the user performs the close state channel operation directly on the MSSC, the SCaaS detects transactions events and closes the state channel as described in Section IV-C.

VI. IMPLEMENTATION AND SIMULATION

In order to perform a performance analysis and evaluation through simulation, we implemented a *payment channel system*¹ based on the proposed solution. The purpose of the payment channel is to enable pre-defined users the transfer of the pre-specified sum of cryptocurrency outside the blockchain network, where they can perform micro-transactions between them.

The payment channel system was established on a computer with the following specifications: Linux Ubuntu 18.02 LTS with Intel Core i7-7700 3.60GHz CPU and 16 GB RAM. IPFS network was composed of five go-ipfs v0.4.19 distribution nodes. The CSSERSA component was deployed on one NodeJS v11.12.0 web server, and the MSSC component was deployed on the Ethereum Ropsten test network. The connection between the Ethereum Ropsten blockchain network and our system was established with Infura service API [24].

Because the CCLISA component is running on the client-side and requires user interaction (e.g., confirming transactions), an alternative approach for simulation purposes was needed in order to run it in an automated mode. For this, we implemented a NodeJS script,² which includes user's identity (public and private key pair), which will automatically perform the micro-payment transactions, and user's address which will receive the payments.

A. TRANSACTION THROUGHPUT VERIFICATION

The main goal of the simulation was to verify that with the proposed solution, the higher throughput of transactions can be achieved than on the blockchain network. For this purpose, a test scenario was set up, where we first analyzed how long does it take for 100 on-chain payment transactions to be performed on a public Ethereum blockchain network. We analyzed this on the Ethereum Ropsten test network. After having captured the time taken for 100 on-chain payment transactions, we continued to analyze how many off-chain micro-transactions can be performed in the same time, on a payment channel system, which is based on our proposed solution. At this point, it is also important to emphasize that during the testing, the blockchain transaction gas prices were

¹Source code: <https://github.com/podgostar/prototype-scaas>

²Source code: <https://github.com/podgostar/scaas-test-framework>

FIGURE 4. Comparison between the number of state changes performed within the proposed SCaaS and the blockchain network.

set to 50 Gwei, which is historically above-average gas price in order for the miners to accept the transaction in the first next mined block. With this gas price value, we wanted to minimize the impact of the variable factors of the blockchain network on the performed analysis. The above-presented test set was repeated 12 times, whereby the best and the worst results of those were discarded in order to objectify the average result.

In one test set, the first 100 blockchain payment transactions were run, where all intermediate transaction times were also recorded. Then the transactions on our payment channel were run. We recorded how many transactions were performed for each intermediate time gained from the first on-chain run. The average times of performed transactions and the average number of transactions performed on our system in these time intervals were calculated. The total average execution time of all transactions performed on blockchain was 1.926.876 milliseconds or approx 32 minutes. In this time, within the proposed SCaaS based system, 1.233 transactions on average were performed.

Figure 4 presents the relation between the average number of performed payment transactions on the public blockchain network and the off-chain micro-transactions performed through the implemented payment channel based on our proposed solution. The obtained results show almost a factor of 12.3 better performance of the proposed solution as the one performed classically, i.e., on the blockchain network. Although the results were anticipated, since this is the purpose of state channels the increase in the number of performed transactions is not completely linear, because the response times of the Infura service API, as an access

point to the Ethereum Ropsten blockchain network may vary.

Based on the data, we can claim that the number of transactions that a user can perform with our system is 12.3 larger than a number of transactions that can be performed at the same time on the blockchain network. It should also be noted that for the 1.233 transactions performed on the proposed system user used 0 Ethereum gas unit. There are no costs for the user with performed transactions through the proposed system, while the 100 performed transactions on the Ethereum Ropsten blockchain network required 2.100.000 Ethereum gas units. The cost for transactions performed on the blockchain network was 105.000.000 Gwei.

B. STRESS TEST VERIFICATION

Additionally, we performed stress analysis, which purpose was to check if the proposed solution is feasible in terms of production status even though the current version of implementation is in proof of concept phase. The objective of the stress test was to check if the proposed system can concurrently handle multiple different users request related to the payment channel system functions (e.g., open, join, execute micro-transaction, close). To perform the analysis, we decided to open 2000 payment channels. Because we perform this analysis on a public Ethereum Ropsten test network, we need to control 4000 Ethereum accounts with appropriate native cryptocurrency Ether on their accounts. The first step was to prepare a script which generates 4000 Ethereum accounts. After that, we need to distribute a sufficient quantity of cryptocurrency Ether to generated accounts. Following operations were executed:

- 1) step: concurrently open 1600 channels;
- 2) step: concurrently join to 1400 opened channels;
- 3) step: execute 200 different micro-transactions;
- 4) step: concurrently join to 200 opened channels, open 400 channels, execute 1200 micro-transactions, and close 200 payment channels.

The results were as follows:

- 1) step: 1566 channels were opened successfully. After a review, we find that error occurred in the communication between the user with the blockchain network. For the connection between the user and blockchain network purposes, Infura service API was used, and the same issue is already reported and marked as open in public Github code repository.³ Based on that evidence, we can conclude that the proposed system successfully performed the step. Because of the error mentioned above the numbers of executed operations in step 2 and step 4 was subject of change;
- 2) step: all 1366 operations were successfully executed;
- 3) step: all 200 operations were successfully executed;
- 4) step: all of the total 1966 operations were successfully executed;

Based on the results of the performed stress test, we can conclude that despite the proof of concept implementation phase, the payment channel system of the proposed solution was successful and is feasible in terms of production status.

VII. COMPARISON

This section covers a Comparison of our proposed solution. The evaluation was performed through comparisons with solutions among listed related works in Section II, limited to the Ethereum state channels solutions. The Raiden and the Celer Network solutions were selected because they are the only solutions among other related works that, at the moment of writing, operate on the Ethereum main network. The evaluation consists of the characteristics and performance comparison described below.

A. QUALITATIVE COMPARISON

The main purpose of the state channel solutions as well as others (e.g., side-chaining, and Plasma) is to resolve scalability problems. After scalability problems are resolved, the prerequisite for mainstream adoption of blockchain technology is fulfilled [25]. However, this in itself does not mean that mainstream adoption will be indeed achieved if solutions (i.e., state channels) does not include features, which are crucial for the end-users. For the comparison, we have selected nine features of the state channel solution that we believe are crucial for the end-users. Following are the features and their descriptions, including the reasons for their choosing:

- **IMPROVED THROUGHPUT** - more transactions can be performed than on the blockchain network;
- **DECENTRALIZATION** - solution incorporates the properties of decentralization;

³<https://github.com/INFURA/infura/issues/78>

- **MUTUAL SETTLEMENT** - participants can close a state channel by mutual agreement, with a transaction performed directly on the blockchain network;
- **MINIMAL ON-CHAIN INCLUSION** - operations performed on the blockchain network within state channel are reduced to a minimum (e.g., open, join, close);
- **AS A SERVICE** - solution can be used as a service;
- **AD-HOC CLOSE** - participants can anytime and without any restrictions transfer the off-chain state on the blockchain network;
- **GENERALIZED STATE CHANNEL** - solution can be used for different purposes;
- **FRAUD MONITORING** - solution includes monitoring service, which purpose is to prevent all fraud attempts even though the participants are online or offline;
- **NO SEPARATE NETWORK** - solution does not require that participants join or operate in any additional and separated network.

Information about the Raiden Network solution was obtained from the project official technical documentation - version v0.100.2 [26].

Information about Celer Network operations was obtained from the latest available article [11], and from official public project GitHub repositories (cChannel-eth release v0.12.5,⁴ Celer-Web-SDK release v0.8.2;,⁵ celer-client release v0.8.19).⁶

Results of the comparison of SCaaS with chosen related works based on selected features of state channel solution are displayed in Table 1.

TABLE 1. Comparison proposed solution with related works.

#	Feature	SCaaS	Raiden Network	Celer Network
1	Improved throughput	✓	✓	✓
2	Decentralization	✓*	✓	✓
3	Mutual settlement	✓	✓*	✓
4	Minimal on-chain inclusion	✓	✓	✓
5	As a service	✓	✗	✗
6	Ad-hoc close	✓	✗	✗
7	Generalized state channel	✓	✗	✓
8	Fraud monitoring	✓	✓*	✓*
9	No separate network	✓	✗	✗

Legend: ✓ - Satisfy conditions; ✓* - optional satisfy conditions; ✗ - Does not satisfy conditions;

Below, the explanations of the comparison results noted with the number of each state channel feature are provided.

- 1) All compared solutions improve current blockchain network transaction throughput; more detailed analysis is provided in Section VII-B.
- 2) Raiden and Celer Network operate the logic inside their own separated peer to peer networks, which enables full decentralization. Due to its as-a-service architecture, SCaaS operations are not performed inside its own

⁴<https://github.com/celer-network/cChannel-eth>

⁵<https://github.com/celer-network/Celer-Web-SDK>

⁶<https://github.com/celer-network/celer-client>

separated peer to peer network. However all SCaaS off-chain states are cryptographically secured and stored in a separate distributed and decentralized IPFS network, and thus partly maintains the properties of decentralization.

- 3) The mutual-settlement feature is enabled in both Celer Network and in our solution. Both solutions support the on-chain executed logic, which enables participants to close the channel with a mutual agreement. This is based on verifying digital signed off-chain states of all participants. Raiden Network participants do not have this alternative and are forced to wait for the dispute time.
- 4) In the best-case scenario for the participant, all compared solutions require a minimal number of on-chain transactions. In all compared solutions, these on-chain transactions are only required when participants perform basic on-off chain related operations. Furthermore, neither solution requires from participants performing any additional transactions in the operations related to the change channel off-chain state.
- 5) By incorporating the CCLISA component, SCaaS is designed to be used as a service. This allows participants the usage of state channel solution in a user-friendly manner, without changing the routines and tools they use while communicating with the blockchain network or decentralized applications. For the usage of Raiden and Celer Network solutions, participants must export their blockchain identity to a separate raw keystore JSON file. This file is later used in the process of establishing a connection with separated Raiden and Celer peer-to-peer networks, using a different external third-party dedicated software.
- 6) The SCaaS enables closing the state channels in an ad-hoc manner, which means that any participant can at any time immediately close the state channel and transfer the off-chain state on the blockchain network. Raiden and Celer Network enable the closing mechanism, which is dependent on dispute times. Upon expiration of which the state channel is closed, and the off-chain data available for the usage on the blockchain network. Within Raiden Network this feature is named “*settle timeout*”, and within Celer Network “*challenge period*”. In the meantime, till the settle or challenge time is not exceeded, users cannot manage their assets either in the off-chain or on-chain manner, because these assets are locked.
- 7) Raiden Network is a solution which purpose is to enable only scalable payments. Celer Network and a SCaaS are both designed to provide off-chain mechanisms that can be used within almost any use-case where higher scalability is required.
- 8) A fraud detection monitoring service is by default part of the SCaaS solution. Raiden Network allows participants of state channel to assign other users or services who/which monitor the state channel on their

behalf. For monitoring, Celer Networks incorporates a side blockchain network (named Guardian network), where any user who owns Celer token can stake those and become a user who offers on-demand monitoring services for state channel participants. If state channel participants need monitoring service for their state channels, they have to pay extra. Celer monitoring service does not entirely rely on a technological solution but on crypto-economics incentive insurance models. For this reason, SCaaS is the only solution which, by default, provides fraud monitoring service based on the technical solution and not economic initiatives.

- 9) If participants want to use Raiden or Celer Network solutions, they first need to become part of the separated peer to peer network and run dedicated software where they act as a node of this network. SCaaS is the only solution that does not require that participants join any additional network. This SCaaS feature is related to the “AS A SERVICE” feature.

B. PERFORMANCE COMPARISON

The main goal is to evaluate if the proposed solution is comparable with selected related works in terms of improving transactions throughput of the blockchain network. For the performance comparisons, the official implementations of projects published on GitHub code repositories were used. Raiden Network client version 0.100.2 - *Pluto*,⁷ and Celer Network client version 0.8.19⁸ with Celer Web JavaScript SDK version 0.8.2⁹ to interact with a local Celer node.

For purposes of the performance comparison, it was necessary to perform the identical simulations on the Raiden Network and Celer Network as those which were already performed on the SCaaS solution described in Section VI. The goal of the simulations was to measure how many micro-transaction can be performed through above-mentioned state channel solutions in the same time as 100 on-chain payment transactions. Based on the results from Section VI, the average time of performed 100 on-chain payment transactions was 32.11 minutes. It should be noted that all simulations were performed in the same run-time environment with the specifications, as specified in Section VI. An overview of the analyzed results and its comparison can be seen in Table 2.

TABLE 2. Performance analysis comparison.

Solution	Execution time	Nr. of transactions
SCaaS	32.11 minutes	1233
Raiden Network	32.11 minutes	1449
Celer Network	1.39 minutes*	89

The simulation of the Raiden Network solution was performed within two established Raiden Network clients (one per user), and after that, the direct payment channel between

⁷<https://github.com/raiden-network/raiden/releases/v0.100.2>
⁸<https://github.com/celer-network/celer-client/releases/v0.8.19>
⁹<https://github.com/celer-network/Celer-Web-SDK/releases/0.8.2>

the clients was opened. In order to run automated micro-transactions through opened payment channel, we implemented a NodeJS script, which includes users identity (public and private key) and consecutively performs micro-transactions until predefined time of 31.11 minutes expires. Within a specified time 1449 micro-transactions were performed. We also set up a Celer Network Client, and implement a NodeJS script within which the automated microtransactions was performed. Simulations with the Celer Network solution were not entirely successful. After the 1.39 minutes of performing micro-transactions, the issue with performing micro-transactions was detected. This issue was according to the project public GitHub code repository already reported and marked as open.¹⁰ Until the time when the issue was detected (1.39 minutes), 89 micro-transactions were performed.

The results of the comparison between the proposed solution and Raiden Network solution showed that in the same amount of time, our proposed SCaaS performs fewer micro-transactions than the Raiden Network solution by the factor 0.15. Due to issues in simulations with the Celer Network solution, a reliable comparison with the other two solutions was not possible.

Based on the presented performance analysis, we can conclude that although our proposed solution SCaaS is in the proof of concept phase, the transactions throughput is in the comparable range as other related solutions in this area. However, it should be noted again that our proposed solution includes novel concepts, which bring positive features to the front that other solutions lack.

VIII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed a novel state channel solution in the form of a State Channel as a Service (SCaaS), which is based on the distributed and decentralized principles. It solves the challenges of existing state channel solutions (i.e., dispute times, penalizing dishonest users, closing channel with the non-valid off-chain state), while ensuring the blockchain features (i.e., immutability, transparency, traceability, and integrity). The proposed solution incorporates the basic advantages of classical state channels, i.e., lowering fees, increasing the speed of transaction processing, and enabling better system scalability.

Besides presenting the architecture model for the proposed solution, implementation was performed, based on the idea of a payment channel. In order to prove the security of the proposed solution, an ad hoc security analysis was performed and presented. It shows in detail, that possible security weaknesses are mitigated and that the proposed solution is secure. To verify that a proposed solution in comparison with the classical blockchain transaction principles increases, the number of transactions simulation through the payment system implementation was performed. The results of those

simulations showed that the proposed solution boosts the number of transactions by a factor of 12.3.

Additionally, with the purpose of verifying the feasibility of the proposed solution in terms of production status, the stress test was performed, and results showed that despite the proof of concept implementation phase proposed solution is feasible in terms of production status. Furthermore, a qualitative and quantitative comparison with selected related works were performed. Results show that the proposed solution, with comparison to related works, contributes remarkable additional features and despite, the early implementation phase, performs comparably effectively.

In the future, we will conduct a more detailed study of the properties and reliability of the IPFS network and their impact on the proposed solution. We are also interested in exploring the possibility of using the proposed solution with other blockchain platforms. Optimization of the implementation of the proposed solution is also planned, which may lead to releasing a generalized state channel framework. With such a framework, developers of decentralized applications can include the SCaaS in their projects, which may drive to several different uses cases implemented based on our solution. Moreover, we plan a study on the integration of cryptographic zero-knowledge protocols (ZKP) with trusted computing environments (TEE), which may result in strengthening SCaaS component security. After an optimized and stable system is built, we plan to explore the possibilities of integrating the proposed solution with the Internet of Things technology (IoT) and compare it with other blockchain-related solutions for the IoT integration.

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